

TOURISM OPPORTUNITIES IN MANGALORE AS A SMART CITY

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Abstract:

Tourism refers to the trips that include traveling of people outside the place of their residence for the various purposes like pleasure, business, vacations, research or other purposes. Tourism has become one of the important and major sources of income for many countries, and hence it is considered as a separate industry in the present economy. It comprises of the activities which together form one of the fastest growing international sectors. Tourism may be within the traveler's country or even international. Smart Cities focus on their most pressing needs and on the greatest opportunities to improve lives. They lap a range of approaches- digital and information technologies, urban planning best practices, public-private partnership and policy change-to make a difference. They always put people first. Mangaluru is one of the cities that has been selected for the Smart City Plan along with other 3 cities of Karnataka. Being a historically important place Mangaluru is one of the famous tourist attractions in Karnataka. Mangaluru lies between the Arabian Sea and the Western Ghats. The name of the city has been derived from the local Hindu Goddess Mangaladevi, and it is one of the major ports in India. The port of Mangaluru handles almost 75% of India's coffee exports and a major portion of the country's cashew exports. Now the city of blues and greens is undergoing the smart City Programme comprising enhancement in the economy and employment favoring, affordable, self-sustained, adequate infrastructure, maintenance, conserving cultural heritage and professionalism in quality services.

Index Terms: Opportunities, Information Technologies, Enhancement of Economy & Quality Service

1. Introduction:

The World Tourism Organization defines tourism more generally, in terms which go "beyond the perception of tourism as being limited to holiday activity only", as people "traveling to and staying in places outside their usual environment for not more than one consecutive year for leisure, business and other purposes". Tourism can be domestic or international, but international tourism has both incoming and outgoing implications on a country's balance of payments. Today, tourism is one of the major sources of income for many countries and they affect the economies of both source and host country. The Indian Tourism Industry has gained more power because of a new and fresh concept named Smart City Project by the Government of India. Smart City Plan is an urban renewal and development program by the Government of India. The mission of this is to develop 100 cities all over the nation and making them citizen friendly and sustainable. It is launched by the Prime Minister Narendra Modi in June 2015. Rs980 billion has been approved by the Indian cabinet for the development of 100 smart cities and rejuvenation of 500 others. Smart Cities focus on their most pressing needs and on the greatest opportunities to improve lives. They lap a range of approaches- digital and information technologies, urban planning best practices, public-private partnership and policy change-to make a difference. They always put people first. The list of nomination marked the first stage in the selection of Smart Cities in which the State Governments nominated the potential cities and the Central Government short listed 100. The list comprised of 98 cities including many state capitals. 4 cities of Karnataka State have been selected for Smart City Mission. Mangaluru is diverse in its people, culture and location. Tourism is one industry which is crying for attention and which has the maximum potential to grow in the coming years. While Karavali Utsava is a yearly event, Mangaluru needs something that can sustain its tourism industry. Beach tourism owing its proximity in Bengaluru which has a huge demand for getaways, Mangaluru can be that go to place, which otherwise is being fulfilled by Kerala, Pondicherry and Goa. Religious tourism Udupi, Dharmasthala, Subrahmanya, the churches to name a few which can attract national and international tourism. Nature tourism- Mangaluru is situated on the foothills of the Western Ghats.

Sub-Goals for Mangaluru Smart City:

- ✓ Ensure cleanliness through adoption of decentralized waste management and promote zero waste technology.
- ✓ Promotion of tourism to top the potential derived from natural features of the city. Enhance regional connectivity through air and rail and encourage tourist facilitation services.
- ✓ Drive economic growth based on innovation, knowledge and health care services: Promote establishment of world class infrastructure to attract investment in knowledge and healthcare services.
- ✓ Eco sensitive technology for cost efficient infrastructure.
- ✓ Adopt technology to ensure accountable governance and faster delivery of citizen services.

2. Objectives of the Study:

- ✓ To study the citizen expectations or the public opinion about the Smart City Plan in the development of quality tourism in Mangaluru.

- ✓ To study the various steps taken under this plan for the development of tourism in the city.
- ✓ To study the motivational factors that affect the Mangaluru tourism as given in the Smart City Project.
- ✓ To study the opportunities for the development of older tourist attractions as given in the Smart City Plan.
- ✓ To study the limitations of Smart City Project in the development of tourism in Mangaluru. i.e., what has been ignored in the Smart City Mission.

Scope of the Study:

The scope of the study is to have a detailed analysis of the Mangaluru Tourism and the growth of the tourism industry after the implementation of the Smart City Plan. The study is conducted within Mangaluru City only. Study will be made based on the primary information collected from the visitors of the various tourist places of Mangaluru as well as some tourist guides. The study also needs secondary data for the analysis of growth of the tourism industry in Mangaluru over the years.

Methodology of the Study:

Primary Data: Primary data can be collected using questionnaires from 60 respondents.

Secondary Data: It is collected through various journals, books, magazines and some tourist websites i.e., internet sources.

3. Literature Review:

Bijender K. Punia of Kurukshetra University in his study on 'Problems and prospects of Tourism in Haryana' has stated that "The potential of tourism development in any area, region, state, or a country mainly depends on the availability of unique and varied tourist resources. But at the same time, the facilities and the services too have very important bearing on the overall tourism development prospects of a place or region. Such elements like climate, seasonality, accessibility, attitude of host population, availability of manpower resources and the planning expertise that have vital role to play in this context." He suggested that close coordination between private and the public sector tourism organizations at different levels is the key to success in tourism development when the state departments of tourism must play a central role.

Maneet Kumar in his book 'Tourism Today- An Indian perspective' says that "Effective management of tourism will involve a range of techniques including marketing and publicity information and interpretation as well as planning, control and traffic management." This means tourism involves people, places and planning a facility in harmony with its environments.

Bhatia A.K in a book 'Tourism Development' makes a detailed coverage of tourism psychology, motivation for travel, organization of tourism, measurement, planning and development, tourism marketing and promotions and economic and social significance of tourism.

Sharma K.K in his book 'Tourism in India' advises to improve the hospitality services associated with tourism as "For the healthy development of tourism in a country like India-a land of contrasts, it is desirable for the Government to provide facilities for training in hotel management, tourism and travel agency work. Great emphasis must be laid on linguistic efficiency in the major languages of Europe."

About tourism planning, in the book 'Significance of Tourism in India', Veera Sekharan says, "Tourism is a multi sectoral activity and planning for it is complicated and includes both physical and institutional elements. The current tourism planning emphasizes on integrated and comprehensive approach to meet development objectives without generating socio economic and environmental hazards"

Batra G.S and Dangwal R.C, Editors of the book 'Tourism promotion and development' illustrates eighteen contributions on tourism representing various aspects. R.C Dangwal in his presentation 'Marketing of Tourism in India; New paradigms' says that "India has great tourism potential due to its unique cultural and natural attractions. The potential has not been fully exploited and whatever attempt made in this direction has not met the expected." He further explores immense vistas in India for skiing, river rafting, trekking, paragliding, water sports and wildlife tourism.

Mathieson A and Wall G in their book 'Tourism- Economic, Physical and Social impacts' describes that "The study on tourism is the study of people requirements of the travellers and of the impacts that they have on the economic, physical and social well-being of their hosts. It involves the motivations and experience of the tourists, the expectations of and adjustments made by residents of the reception areas and then roles played by the numerous agencies and institutions which intercede between them." They consider tourism as a 'consumer product' and hence an economic activity having social and physical impacts.

Manohar Sajini, in the preface of the book 'Indian Tourism Business' reveals that "World Tourism is a US\$350 billion business. One out of ten people in the world is a traveler. Tourism industry contributes 10.9% to the world's Gross National Product (GNP) and employs over 200 million people accounting for 11.2 per cent of the global work force. Annually, 595 million tourists across the world purchase goods and services worth US\$3.6 trillion which is 10.69 per cent of the gross global product."

4. Analysis of Survey Data:

Table Showing Profile of the Respondents:

Elements	Frequency	Percentage
Below 15	4	7
15-25	28	47
26-50	23	38
50& Above	5	8
Gender		
Male	35	58
Female	25	42
Income Range:		
Upto Rs5000	21	35
5000-10000	4	6
10000-30000	16	27
30000 & Above	19	32
Residential status		
Mangalorians	26	43
Non Mangalorians	34	57
Awareness among the Respondents about Smart City:		
Aware	45	75
Not Aware	15	25
opinion on Importance for tourism in Mangaluru City:		
Yes, should be given	49	82
No	11	18
Purpose of visit to Mangaluru by the Respondents:		
Pilgrimage	12	20
Rest & Relaxation	30	50
Business	5	8
Curiosity	10	17
Others	3	5
Reasons to prefer Mangaluru as a Tourist Destination:		
Beach & Scenic Beauty	36	60
Religious Places	9	15
Cultural Interest	9	15
Infrastructure Available	5	8
Others	1	2
Mode of Transport Opted by the Tourists:		
Taxi/Tourist Vehicles	7	12
Public Transport	12	20
Own Vehicle	34	57
Train	3	5
Air	4	6
various alternatives of Tourism arrangements made:		
Self	40	67
Travel agents	6	10
Family/Friends	14	23
Others	0	0
Places of Stay preferred by the Respondents:		
Hotels	15	25
Resorts	16	27
Family/Friends	26	43
Others	3	5
Respondents opinion on Tourism potentiality of Mangaluru City:		
Yes , it has	52	52
No, it doesn't	8	13
Major Contributors to the Tourism Industry:		
Government	30	50
MNC/Private Business Houses	18	30
Kanara Chambers of Commerce	5	8
Others	7	12
Public opinion on the History and Culture of Mangaluru:		
Yes	30	50

No	7	12
To some extent yes	23	38
Fields in which Public/ Private body's role is important:		
Transport	12	20
Maintenance	29	48
Popularizing the places	18	30
Others	1	2
Respondents who have faced problems in the City while on a tour:		
Faced	34	57
Not faced	26	43
Public opinion about the Future of Mangaluru Tourism:		
Growth Oriented	26	43
Competitive	14	23
Creative/Innovative	16	27
Outdated	4	7
Major drawbacks of Mangaluru Tourism:		
Traffic	25	41
Infrastructure	11	18
Problems by the Local Public	7	12
Scarcity of Resources	10	17
Pollution	7	12
Others	0	0
Public opinion on the Places that need special care in order to gain Global Recognition:		
Religious Places	12	20
Beaches	19	32
Nature Parks	18	30
Festivals of Mangaluru	11	18
Others	0	0

5. Summary of Findings:

- ✓ As per the study conducted among 60 respondents only 75% of them were aware about the Smart City Plan in Mangaluru City. The remaining 25% of them were not aware about it.
- ✓ The study revealed some of the places of Mangaluru that the people loved to visit. They were, Kudroli temple, Panamboor Beach, Tannirbavi Beach, Summer sand Beach-Ullal, Pilikula Nisargadhama, St. Aloysius Chapel, Lobo's River view-Morgansgate, NITK Surathkal etc.
- ✓ As per the study 82% of the respondents have agreed that Mangaluru Tourism Industry should be given more importance under Smart City Mission and the rest 18% of them said that it should not be given much importance.
- ✓ Under this study 60 respondents have spoken about their purpose of visit to Mangaluru. Majority of them said that they visit Mangaluru for the purpose of Rest and Relaxation during vacations etc. Other purposes were Pilgrimage (20%), Business purposes (8%) and Curiosity (7%).
- ✓ The study found out that 60% of the respondents preferred Mangaluru as the tourist destination because of the Beaches and Scenic Beauty that is available in Mangaluru. Other reasons were the various Religious Places, Cultural interest and Infrastructural Facilities of Mangaluru. Some respondents have also told that Mangaluru is one such places where the best Restaurants for Sea food is available and one of the best reasons given by the respondents was that the Medical tourism available in the city is reasonable and one of the best.
- ✓ The study shows that the majority of the tourists prefer to travel in their own vehicles around the city. Particularly they prefer two wheelers to travel in and round the city. The main reason for this is the traffic problems in the city. Very few of the respondents opted for Taxi, Tourist vehicles, public Transport and other modes of transportation.
- ✓ This study also found out various alternatives of tourism arrangements opted by the tourists. 67% of the respondents wanted to make the tourism arrangements by themselves than depending upon the travel agents, family members and friends. But preferred places of stay were their Family/Friends houses than the Hotels and Resorts.
- ✓ Majority of the respondents have agreed that Mangaluru has a potentiality as a preferred tourist destination. Only 13% of them said Mangaluru does not possess such a potentiality.
- ✓ The study found out who, according to the public are the major contributors towards tourism industry under Smart City Plan. 50% of the respondents pointed at the government, some pointed at the MNCs

and Private Business Houses and only few said it is the Kanara Chambers of Commerce and another few opined that it is the General public and the Mangaluru City Corporation.

- ✓ Among 60 respondents major portion of the respondents have agreed that the unique history and culture of Mangaluru plays an important role in Tourism Industry. Others have partially agreed to the statement.
- ✓ As per the public, in the field of Maintenance the public or the Private body's role is important. It is true that some of the attractive places of Mangaluru has not been popularized among the tourism lovers. Even in this field some more steps by the Private bodies are needed to popularize such places.
- ✓ On the visit to Mangaluru City, majority of the respondents have faced various problems such as Parking and Traffic problems, Garbage etc. it is true that some of the Non-Mangalorians have faced problems from the local residents of Mangaluru.
- ✓ According to the study, public have the opinion that Mangaluru Tourism Industry is Growth Oriented. Only few people have the opinion that it is Outdated.
- ✓ One of the objectives of the study is to find out the limitations of tourism Industry of Mangaluru under Smart City Plan. According to most of the respondents Mangaluru City traffic issues are the major drawbacks which cannot be corrected even after the implementation of Smart City Project with much care. Respondents have also agreed that the problems with infrastructure, local public, scarcity of resources and pollution have an effect on Tourism Industry; but they can be changed with the co-operation and teamwork of the Government, private bodies and the General public.
- ✓ As per the study, Mangaluru tourism can be developed under Smart City Plan by giving first preference to Maintenance and cleanliness of the city. Setting up of a separate department for the betterment of the Mangaluru tourism also would be a nice idea if the Government shows some more interest on that.
- ✓ As per the study, if Beaches are given special care and importance they may even gain Global recognition. The Mangalorian beaches have such capacity. Nature parks and religious places also be given importance as Mangaluru is one of the places where we can find various religious places. Navarathri Festival at Kudroli temple is one of the events held in Mangaluru which attracts the tourists even from other states.
- ✓ As per the study, public are not fully satisfied with Mangaluru Tourism industry. Majority of the respondents have rated it Good and Satisfactory. Very few are fully satisfied and graded Excellent. But 7% of the Respondents are not at all satisfied with the Tourism Industry of Mangaluru.

6. Suggestions:

- ✓ Hospitality should be given more importance in Mangaluru Tourism. Law and order regarding this should be made strict. Safety of the tourists should be taken care.
- ✓ Traffic problems in the City in increasing day by day. Suitable measures can be taken by the Government relating to this issue. Roads can be widened in the city and Flyovers can be constructed wherever necessary.
- ✓ Problems relating to supply of Tobacco products and Drugs should be prevented. Government should take necessary actions to prevent the problems relating to Communal violence and other problems relating to the residents of Mangaluru to ensure the safety of Mangalorians as well as the tourists to make Mangaluru city tourism friendly.
- ✓ Infrastructural facilities near some of the main tourist attractions can be developed and made innovative.
- ✓ Cleanliness and Maintenance of the tourist attractions should be given priority and the vacant places in and around the City should be used for some productive purposes such as construction of Nature Parks, water Parks etc for the public use.
- ✓ Government or Municipality run complexes at minimum rent are to be constructed so that the road side vendors can accommodate and trade through them.
- ✓ More number of Government owned buses can be run in Mangaluru and strict traffic rules should be implemented.
- ✓ Activities which uphold our Culture and Heritage should be given priority.
- ✓ Mangaluru is a Port town and is famous for Beaches as well as Temples. These places should be popularized even outside the state and made convenient to the visitors by various plans and strategies. Government can also set up a separate department for this purpose.

7. Conclusion:

Our exhaustive research in the field of Tourism threw up some interesting views by the public which can be seen in the above analysis. The general impression that we gathered during the Data Collection was the immense awareness and knowledge among people about Smart City Plan in Mangaluru City. People are looking for the Government's interference in the Tourism Industry for the development of Tourism in the City. People in general have kept hopes and expectations on the new concept Smart City and are willing to give their best suggestions to make it possible. The general satisfaction level among public regarding Mangaluru Tourism still

requires improvements, but there are opportunities under the new and recent concepts Smart City Mission, Make in India Campaign etc.

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